

INDIAN DIGITAL ART IN CONTEMPORARY WORLD – A CRITICAL SURVEY

A THESIS SUBMITTED TO BANASTHALI UNIVERSITY FOR THE DEGREE OF
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Certificate

This is to Certify that the thesis entitled “Indian Digital Art in Contemporary World - a Critical Survey” being submitted to the Banasthali University, Rajasthan, India for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in the Visual Art Dept., Faculty of Fine Arts, is a bonafide Research work done by Mrs. Tripti Singh D/o Dr. Kripal Singh under my supervision and guidance. She has fulfilled all the formalities required by the university. To the best of my knowledge and belief no part of this work has been submitted to this or any other university in India or abroad for the award of Ph.D. or any other degree. The assistance and help received during this endeavour have been appropriately acknowledged.

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Preface:

The idea of present research started in 2001 while working in bimari-jankari website in IIT Kanpur when I was working as project associate; I had developed the curiosity to know how the computer can help an artist in making of graphics which can be shown on websites. Prof. T.V. Prabhakar, (Professor., CSE, I.I.T. Kanpur.) had given me the responsibility to carry out the designs and illustrations for the site. My selection was based on viewing my online portfolio presented as website. This was an encouraging incident and proved to be a turning point towards the familiarity of the digital art. At that time Dr. Harish Karnik, (Professor, CSE, I.I.T. Kanpur) and Mrs. Archana Prabhakar (Project Head, Hindi Portal, Computer Centre, I.I.T. Kanpur) helped me to understand the importance of low-resolution graphics, which was required for Internet sites and high-resolution digital graphics for printing the poster for the site. In this way I had gained the experience to create digital graphics for different purposes.

After marriage in 2002, I continued working as freelancer for the print media for different companies. I explored different software to meet the needs of the clients. While working on digital graphics my attention was driven to explore the artists working in digital fine art in India. I started searching the works and the names of artists in digital medium. I tried to contact them and asked the questions about how they work....

Subsequently, I felt that there was need for this research and it became my interest to carry out this study. Meanwhile during the discussion about my interest, Dr. (Mrs.) Sushma Tiwari, Head of Dept. Chemistry, DG College, Kanpur, asked me to meet Dr. Ram Kanwar ji, senior artist and Former Head of Department, Drawing and Painting, D.A.V College, Kanpur. Kanwar ji told me about Prof. Bhawani Shanker Sharma, Dean Fine Arts and Head of Department, Visual Arts, Banasthali University at that time. I contacted him, and told Prof. Sharma about my interest in digital art. He happily accepted guiding me and asked me to get registered. Soon after getting registered for Ph.D. in the Banasthali University, when I started working on synopsis, at the same time I came in contact with Dr. John Antoine Labadie, and he showed keen interest in this research. It was more exposure for me and for other students when he came with his wife Prof. Margie Labadie to take a workshop on digital arts in Visual Art Dept., Banasthali University; later on they helped me to increase my understanding of digital tools, digital painting, and experimentation in printing material. They enhanced my knowledge both in the theoretical and the practical aspects of digital arts.

Hence this study has been to search the past events and the artists who are working in Indian digital arts. I have included some of the major events and arranged them date wise. These events have been found during visits, and searching the Internet till December 2008.

This research has been an opportunity to get in touch with digital art's artists so that I could record their views on different aspects of Indian digital arts. So this research is survey based, and has been carried out to examine the views of Indian digital artists on many related aspects such as use of recent technology in art making process, influence of culture, education, exposition of art and copyright. This study presents the views of various artists on the Indian digital art scene in the world scene.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Tripti Singh". The signature is written in a cursive style with a large, stylized flourish at the end of the name.

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Glossary

Summary:

Digital Art is the true medium of the 21st century: we will wear it, walk inside it, communicate, challenge, compete and join with others globally to take part in the adventure of a new aesthetic - explorers of the virtual landscape.

Chapter one covers the definition of art, printmaking, digital interface and chapter two and five discuss the different forms of digital art. It is noted that digital art follows same rules, as any other contemporary art can be described. Digital art is changing with the speed of technology; therefore it is hard to define the terms to describe digital characteristics. Comparative study for digital art is defined in terms that are specific to digital artist's medium; it's meaning that art is created by its user's input and the commands. In an extreme case it has been noted that without the participation of the user, a piece of digital art might just be a blank canvas.

Chapter four deals with digital art software, like Photoshop, CorelDraw and M.S. paint that are used by today's most of the Indian artists. Hence the medium is totally digitalised thus requiring a computer to showcase and exhibit. HTML (hypertext mark-up language) is also being used to create digital art pieces that are traditionally interactive and functional. Shilpa Gupta's BLESSED CANVASES is a perfect example of how HTML can be used to create an artistic expression through the Internet.

This research has investigated digital possibilities such as software, interactivity printing and issues like copyright. This research also provides the views of Indian artists as well as foreign experts for the cultural aspects of digital art. Cultures are internally affected by both forces encouraging

change and forces resisting change. These forces are related to both social structures and natural events, and are involved in the perpetuation of cultural ideas and practices within current structures, which themselves are subject to change.

Chapter nine covers the plan, design and procedure of the research. The researcher has searched and implements proper procedure to evaluate the questionnaire and interviews.

In chapter nine, there are many topics covered that deal with digital technologies as mediums for the Indian digital artists to express/create their art. It's stated that there are many different types of distinguishing features that constitute a digital medium. Some of the key components in a digital medium are interactivity and customisability. Yet these do not restrict digital mediums/art, thus there are no limits (except those set by technology).

In chapter nine it is been elaborated that the social conflict and the development of technologies can produce changes within a society by altering social dynamics and promoting new cultural models, and spurring or enabling generative action. These social shifts may accompany ideological shifts and other types of cultural change.

Technology is many things, not just relating to science and art, but also to advancements in machinery and manufacturing. And so, to think about the relationship of technology and culture properly, we must consider all aspects of technology that affect our culture.

It also covers events, courses and artists survey about software, printer, culture, explosion, copyright, Internet-based art, etc.

Digital art is bridging the gap between many things, including, but not limited to, the past and future art realm and the ongoing relationship between technology and culture.

The study has searched means of locating the media within its historical and practical context. Digital art has the capacity to be an immersive & interactive environment, to be collaboration with networks of users, anticipate computers that are invisible and yet are everywhere; this study has investigated tangible objects that form a new user interface, explored the possibility of sharing the development and modification of the artwork with its originator or originators.

This research has explored various forms of digital art in which artists are working in India. Since the genre of 'digital art' is new, it can be said that the artists involved are not dissimilar from scientists and explorers of the great unknown. They're constantly exploring the limits and boundaries of modern science and/or technologies to create their unique pieces. Not only are they experimenting with the technological limits, but also the ethical boundaries and psychological limits as well. Some use the exploration and process of producing their artwork to obtain further knowledge in a particular art field, while others may use certain innovative technologies to spread their message and make statements to hopefully make a difference. Today's "digital artists" truly are the pioneers of the new millennium.

This study has also explored the learning environment, which is centred on the courses offered by the institutes and fine art departments, which comprise lesson plans and introductory workshops.

This research contains a record of professional practice, which enables to show variety of opportunities to undertake or engage in aspects of the professional arena.

Digital artwork comes in many forms and types. Some Indian artists use scanner or digital camera for image capturing; others use both, which shows that the digital art is not only being experimented but also been trusted on the ground to get what one likes to get in the form of results. Moreover, a section of the reading that appealed to me was the short section dealing with the work of Saroj Pal Gogi's work. She is a digital artist and traditional printmaker. The researcher has been interested Baiju Partdhan's work too. His work is stunning and very catchy. In his work he combines traditional, digital art, and technology.

Furthermore five expert's views have been analysed in the cultural context as how it affects the different aspects of creating digital artwork. Indian digital artists are formally categorised because they have different approaches and they show varying elements in their works as Digital art has been used to express a message through a specific technology. And also, the technological influence on society and culture is analysed here.

In this research one can see the venues that have been around for showcasing digital art; such sites, which are searched on net and presented in the appendix.

In the short this research: -

This research is to give the opportunity to:

- Shows practical, historical and theoretical understanding of the digital art.
- It provides a platform for digital artists to access their imagination and develop their creative identity.
- It establishes key transferable and employability skills.

Enclosed Areas:

- Historical, theoretical and ethical positions.
- Develop an understanding of the power of the medium.
- Understanding the creative potential of the medium

Understanding the relation to culture and developing technologies.

The front cover image titled as "Lotus" and back cover image titled as "Mirage" by Tripti Singh.